

Curation recommendations for HeFDI repositories

Guidelines and explanations for curating submitted datasets
in the HeFDI repositories

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1 Introduction

Within the scope of their joint project Hessian Research Data Infrastructures (HeFDI) for research data management (HeFDI), eleven Hessian universities identified requirements for operating a research data repository, which were then used to test various tools. Ultimately, they opted for the open source software DSpace and established a distributed, coordinated operation model (see Bode et al., 2019). This resulted in four independently operated instances, with TU Darmstadt and Philipps-Universität Marburg also providing instances or communities in a joint, cooperative operation for Hessian universities not operating an institutional repository themselves. The primary purpose of these institutional repositories is to enable researchers to store and/or publish their data free of charge, while aiming towards their constant improvement as NextGen repositories according to the COAR vision⁸. All repositories meet the following requirement of Guideline 17 ("Archiving") of the German Research Foundation (DFG)'s "Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice" and thus contribute to the implementation of the DFG Code of Conduct:

"When scientific and academic findings are made publicly available, the research data (generally raw data) on which they are based are generally archived in an accessible and identifiable manner for a period of ten years at the institution where the data were produced or in cross-location repositories."⁹

Most HeFDI research data repositories have been operational since the end of 2020. Since then, the number of submitted datasets has grown considerably, thus increasing the need for quality-assured data curation processes.

Quality assurance of research data in repositories is essential to ensure reliability, reproducibility and long-term usability of scientific results, following good scientific practice to achieve the goals of Open Science. In light of recent politically motivated data deletion, securing high-quality datasets in trusted infrastructures is increasingly urgent. Open data should be recognized as a valued scholarly output, requiring transparent review processes. Moreover, FAIR¹⁰ and richly described datasets via metadata are key to making research AI-ready, supporting automated discovery and meaningful reuse.

It became apparent that there is uncertainty across all sites regarding the decision whether a submitted dataset meets the repository's quality criteria or which suggestions for improvements are appropriate or necessary. Taking local differences in data curation into account, this document aims to identify common aspects and quality characteristics. Thus, it supports the HeFDI partners in creating a curation checklist tailored to local priorities. Moreover, the document may be useful for other institutions operating a repository as a basis for developing their own curation criteria. It can also provide submitters to the repository with an overview of the curation process and thus contribute to greater transparency.

This guide is neither binding for the HeFDI repositories nor for their curators. So far, our experience with repository operations and curation shows that, due to their individual and diverse nature, the curation of data publications is a complex process that requires local directional decisions and intellectual handling. Accordingly, it would be neither advisable to formulate rigid curation rules nor to use this document as such in curation. We recommend using the criteria presented here as starting points for an intelligent, reflective curation that flexibly addresses the specifics and needs of each dataset according to local and institutional frameworks.

A DSpace-based research data repository is available at each HeFDI university.

This document aims to promote mutual support in curation processes as well as transparency towards end users.

We recommend reflective and flexible curation within the local and institutional framework.

⁸ COAR Next Generation Repositories: Vision and Objectives. (o. D.). <https://ngr.coar-repositories.org/>

⁹ German Research Foundation (2022). Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6472827>

¹⁰ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

2 Aspects of data curation

This chapter represents the core part of the document. It lists various aspects that may be relevant to the data curation process in research data repositories. These aspects are addressed in the following three subsections:

- Place of publication / assignment
- Descriptive metadata and visualization
- Technical inspection

The individual aspects are structured in such a way that each aspect contains at least an explanation and a suggestion for a text module for communication with submitters.¹¹ In some cases, selected case examples from the repositories are provided.

2.1 Publication site / assignment

2.1.1 Text repositories vs. data repositories

Explanation

Repositories may be geared toward the storage and publication of research data or text documents, for example by offering a metadata schema aimed at text or data publications. This focus can also be reflected in specialized communities within a given repository. Data should be published or archived in the appropriate location to achieve the greatest possible visibility and dissemination (e.g., through appropriate metadata).

The distinction between "text" and "data" is not always clear, as data can also exist in text form. That is why several repositories now enable the publication of all scholarly output types. However, clear distinctions between publication types are necessary in every repository to ensure proper metadata and FAIR-compliant data publication. The following perspective may help: Data publications, even in text form, provide raw information, whereas text publications interpret this data and place it in a more comprehensive context. Due to the different reception types, the curation of data and text publications prioritizes different aspects, respectively. For example, machine processability is usually more important for data than for text documents.

Text module

Your submission appears to be a text document rather than raw research data. We therefore recommend publication at [e.g., name of local text repository] / as [e.g., publication type]. Please submit your document there. / With your consent, I offer to redirect your publication to [e.g., name of repository / other location in the same repository for this publication type].

Case example

- <https://doi.org/10.17170/kobra-202311289104> was originally submitted to DaKS, the research data repository of the University of Kassel.

This manual is structured into three sections.

Does the submission qualify as research data?

¹¹ Many of these text modules had already been written, collected, thematically grouped, and made available within HeFDI by several HeFDI partners before these curation recommendations were drafted. They served as an important basis for the collegial exchange "HeFDI Open Repo" to initiate discussions about different approaches to data curation. This is where the idea for this document came from.

2.1.2 Recommendation of subject-specific repositories

Explanation

Subject-specific repositories have several advantages over generic institutional repositories:

- They are more often known in the scientific community.
- Their metadata schemas tend to contain subject-specific fields that contribute to better description of the data and thus better findability.
- The operating institutions often offer expert advice on how to handle the data.

If a subject-specific repository meets certain quality criteria (including a guarantee of long-term availability of the data, e.g., through the stability of the operating institution; the possibility of granting a license for the data; persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI) for the data), we recommend depositing/publishing the research data there instead of in the institutional repository.

At the same time, there may be reasons to prefer the institutional repository, not least due to the data submitter's/contributors' preference. In the spirit of Open Science, we strive to make the publication process in our repositories as easy as possible. Whether a subject-specific repository is recommended as part of RDM consultation prior to submission of a dataset, or even after submission to the institutional repository is made, is at the discretion of the curators or the operating institution.

Text module

Subject-specific repositories offer more opportunities to describe data according to the standards of the respective discipline. They increase your chances of reaching the subject-specific target group. In your case, we recommend [Name of one or more subject-specific repositories with URL].

2.1.3 Handling of personal information

Explanation

The terms of use of the HeFDI repositories exclude the deposition of datasets containing personal information in almost all cases. Therefore, the curation of newly submitted datasets includes a review in this regard. In all cases involving personal information, ethical considerations and data protection must be observed (see [Info box: Data protection and ethics](#)).

If there is an explicit request to deposit or publish datasets containing personal information and this is not excluded by the repository's terms of use, the institution operating the repository can require that the respondents' informed consent forms be deposited additionally (but not published!). Whether the consent forms should be requested and retained by the operating institution even for subsequently anonymized data, or whether the burden of proof lies entirely with the researchers, is a decision each institution makes within the framework of its own risk assessment. The operating institution has no obligation to review the quality of the anonymization or the legality of the publication (beyond obvious violations). However, it has the option of rejecting datasets or publishing them only subject to conditions if the curator deems this appropriate.

Subject-specific repositories should be preferred.

Does the dataset contain personal information?

If data would be rendered useless for subsequent research by anonymization, or can only be published pseudonymized or even retaining the full personal references, infrastructures equipped for publication of personal information in compliance with the GDPR should be identified and utilized. If these infrastructures are not available at the home institution, researchers can be referred to research data centers such as those listed by the German Data Forum (RatSWD) (see KonsortSWD, 2024).

Text modules

While curating your dataset, we noticed that your submitted dataset contains personal information. Did all data subjects consent to the publication of their data? Without this (informed) consent, GDPR-compliant storage of such data cannot be guaranteed.

If anonymization would restrict the reusability of the data too much, we recommend contacting a more suitable repository, for example one of the data centers listed at the German Data Forum (<https://www.konsortswd.de/en/services/research/all-datacentres/>) and publish your data there, as their infrastructure is designed for such data. We are happy to help you find a suitable repository.

Specialized research data centers exist for the publication of personal research data.

Info box: Data protection and ethics

Especially when publishing data from qualitative surveys, patient studies, or similar personal research topics, ethical considerations and data protection concerns are crucial for ethically sound research. While some ethical requirements are often already covered by the data protection regulations, in some instances these requirements extend beyond legal obligations, adhering to good scientific practice and ensuring research integrity. Beyond legal requirements, many professional societies and repositories provide ethical guidelines to follow when publishing data. This adherence may require that certain data is published only in specific repositories and/or with special permission.

It is essential to establish ethically and data protection-compliant practice for handling of research data with the relevant authorities at the early stages of a research project. This includes considering the potential publication of the data from the onset. Later in the research project, the curator acts as an additional review body, intellectually evaluating potential risks and raising questions if necessary. The final decision-making rests with the researchers, who should consult with the data protection officers and ethics committees. If needed, the curator may refer the researcher to these bodies for further guidance.

In order to discuss possible ethical or data protection contraindications, a critical assessment of the content of the data is necessary.

2.1.4 Placement within the structure of the repository

Explanation

If the repository specifies a structure, it may occur that a dataset is submitted to an inappropriate location. Whereas some repositories set predefined collection structures (e.g. the allocation of datasets to the departments or institutes where they were created), other repositories will create collections as required (e.g. for individual projects or research groups).

On a technical level, sorting options are usually limited by the software used. For example, the software (e.g., DSpace) may offer the option of mirroring records, so that they appear in multiple collections simultaneously. Ultimately, it is up to local discretion whether a given feature is offered or not.

Text module

You submitted your dataset to collection XY. The topic / the people involved / the description suggests that it may also be assigned to collection YZ. Is the current collection correct, or would you like to adjust?

Is the dataset in the right place?

2.2 Descriptive metadata and visualization

2.2.1 Title

Explanation

The title should be descriptive enough to enable users to recognize that this is a dataset and roughly what data is contained in it. Further insight into the content is provided in the abstract (see [Section Abstract / Summary](#)). In the event of a related text publication, the procedure differs locally: In some repositories, the title should not be the same for both publications. Instead, the title for the data publication should be independent and identify the data as accurately as possible. In others, the recommendation is to supplement the title to indicate the data types. Whether the title of a dataset is meaningful enough is at the discretion of the curator.

The title should be appropriate for the dataset and should be distinct from any related text publication.

Text modules

Case 1: Title not meaningful enough

Please formulate the title in such a way that it is clearer what data is being provided, e.g. by mentioning the project name, the method (survey, illustration, experimental data, mapping, etc.), the object of study (people, animals, professional groups, etc.), or similar.

Case 2: Same title as associated text publication

Your data publication has the same title as the associated article. Would you like to have the data publication indicated by adding [Dataset] or something similar to the title? This makes it easier to identify the publication type in search results and publication lists.

Case examples

■ Example JLU Gießen:

Title specification for datasets underlying a publication (dissertation, journal article): *[OPTIONAL-PREFIX] Data for "[TITLE]"*

<https://doi.org/10.22029/jlupub-18225> = Experimental Data for [TITLE]

■ Example University of Kassel:

Recommendation to mark datasets for publications of the same name with an additional suffix (e.g. [Dataset])

<https://doi.org/10.48662/daks-42> = [Title of text publication] [Dataset]

■ Examples of unsuitable titles:

“Data Müller et al.” (creators should be referenced in metadata fields)

“Reproduction data” (too general)

■ Examples of suitable titles:

“Interview Transcripts: Driving Corporate Sustainability Through Artificial Intelligence”

“HEUREC focus group discussion transcripts”

2.2.2 Abstract / Summary

Explanation

An abstract or summary should be descriptive, giving potential subsequent users a rough overview of the content. Ideally, even individuals without subject-specific expertise should be able to understand the description; for this purpose, uncommon abbreviations should be spelled out at least once. If there is a related text publication, its abstract should not be used word for word for the dataset. The abstract of the data publication should describe the data and not (only) the text publication or the overarching research project.

The abstract should provide an initial overview of the dataset.

Text module

Please review your abstract. The abstract should help others gain an overview of the data content. Ideally, you should provide an overview of the data contained and its context. Please also provide the full abbreviated terms [feel free to provide a positive example from your own repo].

2.2.3 Creatorship

Explanation

The submitter of a dataset is not always the creator of the data. However, in a purely digital submission process, the submitter usually agrees to the publication agreement as the rights holder. Therefore, if copyright applies to the data, written confirmation from the creators should be requested and retained.

Were all contributors taken into account?

Additionally, the data may originate from a collaborative effort without an identifiable primary creator. In this case, all co-creators should also be listed as well.

Text module

As the data submitter, you confirmed the publication agreement at the end of the submission process. Since this data is copyrighted, the creator of the data is responsible for granting the rights. Are you the rightful owner of the submitted data? If not, please provide me with written confirmation from the creator.

Your information suggests that others are involved besides yourself. Therefore, I would like to point out that you can and should list all persons involved in publications with multiple contributors.

2.2.4 ORCID iD

Explanation

We encourage the specification of persistent identifiers for all persons involved wherever possible because they provide a unique and permanent identifier for researchers, regardless of name changes or institutional affiliations. ORCID has established itself as a system for this when it comes to research data repositories. Linking datasets with ORCID iDs not only enables accurate data attribution but also facilitates the linking of research data with other scientific contributions and publications. This promotes transparency, traceability, and recognition of researchers' work, which in turn increases the quality and impact of scientific research.

Using ORCID iDs is particularly important to avoid possible misattributions with frequently occurring combinations of first and last names (e.g., "Michael Müller").

Text module

Do you have an ORCID iD (<https://info.orcid.org/researchers/>)? We recommend providing ORCID iDs of all contributors to your data submission. This will facilitate clear, global attribution and strengthen the visibility and traceability of your research contributions.

We recommend using the ORCID iD for author identification.

2.2.5 Dates

Explanation

Depending on the software or configuration, dates may be automatically included (e.g., dc.date.accessioned or dc.date.available for the date of acceptance into the repository). Which other dates are possible or even required, and in what format, varies between repositories.

Several other date formats may be available, including dc.date.issued (date of submission), dc.date.collected (date/period of data collection), dc.date.update (date of the last update of the dataset), and others. Their correct use may not always be obvious to users. Therefore, the curation checks whether the dates in the respective fields appear reasonable and whether the date formats comply with local requirements (if applicable). Furthermore, it is checked whether the dates provided are consistent or whether, for example, conflicting dates appear in different places.

It is at the curators' discretion whether dates get corrected with or without feedback to the submitter.

Text module

You specified the date "Compiled" / "Submitted" / ... "[Date]". In the description / README / ... of your dataset, you state a different date. Is this correct?

During curation, it is checked whether the dates are conclusive.

2.2.6 Language

Explanation

The language can be specified for the entire dataset and individually for selected metadata fields (title, description). Correct language specification for metadata fields can improve discoverability and plays a role in advanced processing operations such as presentation as Linked Open Data (LOD). Therefore, the language of metadata fields should be specified wherever possible.

It is possible that the data itself does not contain any language; a "N/A" or "Other" option should be available for this.

During the curation process, missing language information can usually be added independently by the curator and does not require explicit feedback from the submitter. Still, for transparency, it is advisable to inform the submitter. If the language used is not known to the curator, the submitter is to be contacted.

Text module

You provided a title / description in a language I do not understand. If you let me know what language it is, I am happy to add this information to the metadata. This will improve the discoverability of your dataset.

The language information for metadata fields should be used.

2.2.7 README

Explanation

A README file should contain all the information necessary to understand the data and thus reuse or replicate results. Hence, it is more detailed than the dataset abstract and can consist of multiple pages. Furthermore, the abstract is sometimes subject to restrictions in repositories, such as the maximum number of words or characters, whereas the README file can be as long as necessary. The preferred format for README files is *.txt or *.md. If the layout is relevant, a README can also be created as a *.pdf. Depending on the complexity of the dataset (e.g., given by a multi-level folder structure), it may be useful to provide a top-level README file for the entire dataset and additional README files for each subfolder. These can be supplemented by machine-readable formats that contain relevant information, such as *.json or *.xml files and/or codebooks in *.tsv/*.csv format. The curator will assess, within the scope of their capabilities (including subject-specific expertise), whether navigation through the entire dataset and reuse of the individual data are possible with the provided information.

Typical contents of a README file may include the following, where applicable and necessary in the individual case:¹²

- Instruments and methods used to generate or collect data and subsequently process it; a detailed description of the methods may be provided separately (e.g., as part of a text publication based on the data). This also includes, where appropriate, primary sources of reused data, methods, and criteria for quality assurance and quality control.
- List of folders and files, file name conventions, relationships between files, short descriptions of the files' contents (summarized / as an overview for related files, e.g. time series, analogue observations / measurements at different locations, collections of image data, ...).

Important context information can be provided, for example, in a README file.

¹²Dryad, https://datadryad.org/stash/best_practices#describe-your-dataset-in-a-readme-file (accessed on October 28, 2024)

- List of variables with full names (resolve abbreviations/acronyms), units of measurement, coding for e.g. male/female, missing data, quality control (quality flags for e.g. low quality, questionable, outliers).
- Further information for reusing data: required programs or software, special instructions (especially for executing code), possible license and citation suggestion.

Whether information that is already available elsewhere (e.g., metadata such as creator names, license, persistent identifier) should also be included in the README file or not is handled differently. On the one hand, redundantly recording this information carries the risk of discrepancies that could complicate subsequent use (e.g., in the case of the license). On the other hand, the README file is downloaded together with the data, so the information it contains is more likely to be stored directly with the data, thus ensuring that the data can be correctly identified with greater certainty under different circumstances. It would be ideal if an excerpt of the metadata and the license text were automatically downloaded when the data is downloaded, but this is not currently the case in our repositories. Therefore, curation primarily focuses on ensuring that the README file and the metadata do not contain contradictory information; the exact content of the README file, however, is not prescribed in detail.

Some information may be in both the metadata and the README file.

Text modules

Case 1: No README file available

All information necessary to understand the data should be stored with the data in the repository; otherwise, the data will be of limited use. A common way to provide this information with minimal effort is to include it in a README file, which is uploaded as a simple text file.

Please place the README file at the top level of the dataset outside of any *.zip archive so that it is immediately visible and can be downloaded individually by potential re-users. This supports them in assessing if your dataset can be useful for them.

Case 2: README file with insufficient information

While reviewing your submitted dataset, we noticed that the README file is missing important information. Please supplement it with the following information to ensure maximum reusability: [...]

2.2.8 Keywords

Explanation

Keywords briefly and concisely identify the most important topics of a dataset. In addition to the abstract, they serve as a subject-specific description and are intended to further improve the findability of the dataset by assisting users in researching specific subtopics within a discipline. Assigning keywords is generally not mandatory in the HeFDI repositories. However, if submitters do not provide keywords, they should be made aware of the usefulness of keywords during curation so that they can submit some if necessary.

Meaningful keywords support the findability of the dataset.

The selection of keywords and the language used are at the discretion of the submitter. When selecting keywords, it is recommended to use keywords that have not previously appeared in other metadata fields (abstract, title, etc.) to create real added value in terms of improved discoverability. To ensure the international discoverability of a dataset using keywords, it is recommended to provide the keywords in English. Keywording in other and/or in several languages is accepted.

Text module

You have assigned only a few keywords to your data submission. To make your dataset easier to find during research, it would be helpful if you could add additional keywords related to the method/location/description/restriction of the topic. / To make your dataset easier to find in searches, we have added additional keywords.

2.2.9 Subject classification

Explanation

Choosing the DFG Subject Classification and/or the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) gives the data submission a subject classification. Thus, the repositories can enable browsing via subjects/disciplines and the data submission can be found more easily.

The subject-specific classification based on an established schema supports findability.

Text modules

Case 1: No subject assigned

You did not assign a DFG subject / Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) category during the submission process. Assigning your submission to a subject enables subject-specific browsing and improves findability. We would therefore like to ask you to assign one. / Therefore, we have assigned a subject area that we consider appropriate to your submission. Please review this subject classification and change it if necessary.

Case 2: Suspected incorrect subject classification

During the submission process, you assigned the DFG subject / Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) category [insert assigned subject here]. Please review and confirm or correct as necessary.

2.2.10 Related resources

Explanation

If mentioned in the description, or known from other sources, existing related resources should be identified and linked. Why this is important: The linking of resources enables seamless navigation between related materials and provides a comprehensive understanding of the context and connections around a particular dataset or document. Linking can also occur within the repository itself: DSpace (starting with V7.0) offers a suitable entity-relationship model that allows related publications to be connected through defined relationships. This connected approach improves both the user experience and data interoperability.¹³

Other publications related to the dataset should be linked in the metadata.

Text module

You mention [insert related resource or other reason for believing related resources exist here]. We encourage you to include information about related resources, such as DOIs for journal articles related to the data. This provides context for your data and/or publication(s) and contributes to the overall coherence and discoverability of your research.

¹³GO FAIR, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/> (accessed on November 1, 2024)

2.3 Technical inspection

2.3.1 Size and number

Explanation

The following two aspects must be considered and weighed against each other for the usability regarding uploading and downloading a dataset.

Size and number of files can affect usability.

■ *Number of attached files*

Splitting the dataset into multiple files allows users to retrieve only necessary content, reduces the size of individual files, makes downloading more feasible over weak internet connections and thus prevents, for example, server-side interruptions of the download after a certain time. However, a large number of attached individual files makes the dataset more confusing if the description is inadequate.

■ *Size of attached files*

Uploading and downloading individual files that exceed a certain size may cause difficulties. This also applies if a large number of files have been divided into packages to maintain clarity and logical organization (see also [Section Archive Files](#)), resulting in large package sizes.

When suggesting packages, the curator should consider the technical limitations of uploading and downloading large files via the user interface. For DSpace repositories, file counts in the low double-digit range and file sizes up to 4 GB are generally considered manageable. Often, the system can be adapted for larger volumes and file sizes, or different local size and volume limits already exist.

When dealing with volumes or file sizes that exceed previous experience, curators often engage directly with submitters and attempt to find technical and individual solutions regarding the manageability of uploading and downloading. These solutions often include not only technical adjustments but also the optimization of documentation, or dividing the dataset. Transparent communication with submitters is particularly important given the possibly time-consuming processing of such submissions.

For large datasets, customized solutions are often required.

For packages, the dataset description, README file, or metadata of the individual files should clearly state what they contain.

If a reasonable balance between file number and size is not achievable for a dataset, the curator can suggest splitting the dataset into multiple items, which introduces another level of logical separation and makes the individual sub-datasets (as items) smaller and more manageable. These related datasets can each receive a DOI (if applicable) and be linked via the respective metadata. However, separation is not appropriate or possible in all cases. The decision is at the curator's discretion in consultation with the data submitters.

Text modules

Case 1: Dataset consists of (too) large individual files

You have combined your data into a very large single file / a few individual files. Very large files can cause download difficulties. For better reusability, we recommend storing the files unpacked in the dataset / dividing the dataset into several smaller packages.

Case 2: Dataset contains a large number of individual files

Your dataset contains a large number of individual files. For clarity, we recommend dividing the data into well-described, logical packages.

Case 3: Dataset contains both many and large files

Your dataset contains many large files. The size and number of files may cause problems with clarity and downloading. Please consider splitting the dataset into multiple datasets linked via metadata references. We would be happy to discuss splitting options with you.

Case example

Large number of individual files: <https://doi.org/10.48662/daks-48>

2.3.2 Functional test of the dataset

Explanation

Curation includes a basic functionality check. For this purpose, the submitted files are initially downloaded in full.

If possible, with acceptable effort (depending on the number of files, the size of individual files, and the availability of the appropriate software), each file is opened individually to ensure that downloading and opening works. Additionally, depending on the effort required, a random checksum comparison is performed (local implementation varies) to ensure that the uploaded files actually correspond to the saved files and do not contain errors. Checksum comparison is especially recommended for large files, which may have experienced intermittent connection interruptions during upload.

If the dataset is an archive (e.g., *.zip, *.tar), it is important to check whether the archive is compressed or uncompressed after unpacking to ensure maximum usability. This can be done, for example, by checking after downloading and unpacking if the file size has changed between the archive and the unpacked individual files. We always recommend using uncompressed archives (see [Section Archive Files](#)).

If the number of files is too large to open all of them, individual files are opened randomly while ensuring that the sample is distributed representatively across the dataset: for example, files from multiple folders and different file formats (if applicable) should be checked.

Attention is paid to any abnormalities, like:

- Are there duplicate files?
- Does a folder name suggest, for example, that it is test data that should not be part of the dataset?
- Does the dataset's description or README file refer to files that are not found among those downloaded?

Various difficulties can prevent the files from being checked by downloading and opening them:

- The necessary software is no longer available.
- The file format is unknown.¹⁴
- The individual files in the dataset are disproportionately large.

In this case, the submitter will be informed that verification was not performed and will be advised to perform a self-verification. In case of difficulties related to the file format, the [Section File formats](#) applies.

During curation, a basic functionality check of the submitted files is carried out.

If archive files are necessary, they should be uncompressed.

If there are a large number of files, random checks are carried out.

¹⁴ To obtain information on a variety of file extensions, it is worth taking a look at the database File-Extension.info (<https://www.file-extension.info/de>). However, as a curator, you will find that many submitted files require very specific, often proprietary, software, which then again raises the problem of the availability of the necessary software.

Text modules

Case 1: Files were downloaded and errors were detected

While reviewing your dataset files, I noticed the following:

- The file [filename] seems to exist twice.
- The file [filename] could not be opened.
- The file name [filename] suggests that it should not be part of the dataset.

Please take another look yourself and let me know if the file(s) should be replaced.

Case 2: Files were only partially checked or not checked at all

- I was able to download your files, but due to [state reason here] I only tried to open some of them.
- Due to [state reason here], I was unable to download and open your files to check if they work.

If you would like to double-check whether your files arrived safely in the repository, you can compare the checksum. You can find the checksum of the uploaded files after your dataset has been accepted into the repository under "Long View" below the file names. Compare the checksum in the repository with the checksum calculated on your computer. If they match, the file should be OK.

The integrity of a file can be checked by checksum comparison.

2.3.3 File formats

Explanation

File formats play an important role in repositories, especially concerning reusability and long-term stability. We strive for high (re)usability for the datasets in our repositories for as long as possible. Using open file formats is recommended to achieve both goals. An overview of file formats was developed in HeFDI at the beginning of 2022 (see [Appendix: File format recommendations for research data in HeFDI repositories](#)).

We recommend using open file formats.

In curation, file format advice is purely advisory. Repositories accept almost any file format (subject to local variations), if requested by submitters, despite warnings about potentially reduced usability and the impending loss of readability. The choice of a particular file format, even one not recommended, may have scientific and/or pragmatic reasons. Therefore, repositories do not impose strict guidelines.

Text modules

Generally, open file formats are better suited for reuse and long-term storage than proprietary file formats. We therefore recommend using open file formats whenever possible.

Case 1: File format is unknown to the curator

You are using the *.x and *.y formats. Are these proprietary file formats that require specific (paid) software to open them? If so, is there a way to convert the files to an open format, such as *.z? You can find an overview of suitable file formats in our FAQ at [local FAQ link, if applicable]. You are also welcome to upload the data twice: once in the existing file format and once in the open format.

Case 2: File format and conversion recommendation are known to the curator

You are using the *.xlsx file format, which is a proprietary format. We recommend converting it to *.csv. An overview of suitable file formats can be found in our FAQ at [local FAQ link, if applicable]. You are also welcome to upload the data twice, once as *.xlsx and once as *.csv.

2.3.4 Archive files (*.zip, *.tar, *.7z, *.rar etc.)

Explanation

Ideally, it should be possible to view and access the files in a dataset individually without having to download all of them. However, encapsulating files in archives (e.g. *.zip, *.tar) does not meet this requirement. Furthermore, compressed archives can create challenges for long-term archiving. For these reasons, uncompressed archives are preferred.

In the following cases, creating an uncompressed data package is necessary or favourable:

■ *Necessary*

The dataset has a folder structure that must be preserved. However, the repository software DSpace used in HeFDI only supports hierarchy-less lists of files, so folder structures must be preserved using a data archive.

■ *Favourable*

The dataset contains many individual files, which can only be effectively processed together. Likewise, the aforementioned limitation of DSpace only displaying hierarchy-less lists of files would mean that one would have to scroll endlessly through a dataset containing hundreds or thousands of individual files to find a specific file, which would severely limit usability.

Creating a compressed data package can be a practical solution for very large files that would otherwise be impossible to upload or download due to their size. This approach takes into account the potentially shorter usage period.

Important: When using multiple container files, it should always be clear which file is located in which part of the dataset. If a README file or similar documentation is part of the dataset, it should always be accessible at the top level and hence be accessible without downloading the entire archive.

Text modules

*Case 1: *.zip archive with only a few files in it was submitted*

You have uploaded your data as a *.zip archive. Since your dataset consists of only a few files, we recommend storing them individually for easier access.

*Case 2: *.zip archive contains README file*

You have packaged your files in a *.zip archive, which seems suitable in your case. For easier access, the [README file or other documentation file] should also be provided outside of the archive.

*Case 3: Compressed *.zip archive was submitted*

Compressed *.zip archives are not recommended for long-term data storage, as even minor memory errors in compressed files can render the entire file unusable. Therefore, please package your files as a *.tar archive or an uncompressed *.zip archive ("store only"). *.tar is uncompressed and can be created and unpacked using the same tools as *.zip.

Case 4: Submission contains several archive files whose content has not yet been adequately documented

You submitted your files in a compressed format and multiple containers. We recommend documenting the contents of each container at a higher level, thus providing an overview of which part of the dataset is contained in which container. This documentation can be provided, for example, in one of the existing README files.

Packing files into archive folders has its drawbacks, but they can be justified. The same applies to compression.

For archive files, the documentation of the contents should be stored in an accessible manner.

2.3.5 Access restrictions and embargo

Explanation

Regarding research data stored in repositories, an embargo refers to a period during which a dataset's metadata is publicly accessible while access to the data itself is still restricted. During the embargo period, the files may only be viewed or used by specific individuals or institutions, such as the researchers themselves, potential collaboration partners, or reviewers in peer review processes or doctoral procedures.

The researchers assess the need for an embargo or access restriction. Curation primarily involves critical reflection on whether the researchers' wishes are being met, i.e., whether a desired or necessary access restriction was stated in the submission or whether one was erroneously set when requesting open publication. Furthermore, it is crucial to verify whether the access restriction or embargo has been implemented correctly from a technical perspective (e.g., checking permissions).

When it comes to data curation, there are generally two cases regarding embargoes that require different actions:

- *Case 1: An embargo or access restriction has been requested, but it may not be legally required.*

In the spirit of open data and open science, free data availability is mandated and desirable for publicly funded projects. The wish to restrict access should be reviewed and discussed with the researchers in these cases. While the researchers' wishes are decisive here, inquiries can prevent potential misunderstandings that could hinder the free publication of the data.

- *Case 2: No embargo or access restriction was requested, but it is legally required.*

In the interest of data protection, contract law (confidentiality, patents), and/or public safety, it may be necessary to restrict access to the data. If there is reasonable suspicion that such restrictions may have been overlooked during submission, the curator should inquire accordingly.

Text modules

Case 1: An embargo / access restriction has been requested, but it may not be legally required.

While reviewing your dataset, we noticed that you are requesting an embargo or access restrictions for your data. This would mean that your dataset can be found immediately, but the data itself can only be downloaded later or only upon request. Does this meet your requirements?

We see no reason why an immediate, open publication of your dataset would be unacceptable. We would be glad to discuss this further with you.

Case 2: No embargo or access restriction was requested, but it is legally required.

While reviewing your dataset, we noticed that you did not request an embargo or (temporary) access restriction for your data. From our project consultation with you / from the project description at [...], we understand that your project is funded by an external partner and not by public funds. Is this publication without an embargo being agreed upon with the funding body? Should there be reasons to restrict access or delay publication (embargo), we would be happy to implement this. Otherwise, your dataset will be freely available worldwide immediately after acceptance into the repository.

During curation, attention is paid to possible indications and the correct implementation of access restrictions and embargoes.

Case examples

- Cooperation agreements with external partners sometimes contain clauses that prevent (immediate) publication.
- If the data creators have made different statements regarding access restrictions, e.g. if it was mentioned in a consultation that the dataset should only be accessible to certain people, but no access restrictions were set during submission, it is appropriate for the curator to ask for clarification.

2.3.6 Licensing

Explanation

Licenses for research data and research software are required to ensure legal clarity regarding the future use of these data. It is recommended to choose established, widely used licenses. Therefore, the HeFDI repositories offer a selection of standard licenses for datasets. In the spirit of open science, the selected licenses should allow for as much freedom of reuse as possible. While it is possible to create custom licenses or restrict data reuse to the limits set by copyright law (local variations may apply), such options should be avoided in the interest of legal clarity.

It is also important to note that different licenses are appropriate for different digital objects. For most research data, we recommend Creative Commons licenses (CC licenses). However, for research software, scripts, or code, it often makes sense to publish them under dedicated open-source software licenses (e.g., MIT, GPL, BSD), as the terms of these licenses were designed specifically for software, and the terms of CC licenses do not cover some of the common usage scenarios in software development.

When assessing whether or not code should be published separately and under a different license from the rest of the data, a practical approach is to determine whether the code accompanying is usable only with that specific data or whether it comprises more extensive scripts or general-purpose software that can also be applied to other datasets. Recommendations for the publication of research software have been developed in other contexts. While this document focuses on research data, it is equally advisable to follow the respective guidelines for research software, e.g., the FAIR principles for Research Software¹⁵, and the Foundations of Research Software Publication¹⁶.

If scripts or software are submitted to research data repositories along with research data, a licensing issue arises due to the different licensing requirements. If there is an explicit desire to publish data and code together in one dataset, a license that is appropriate to the data should be selected. In this case, we recommend that the different license of the code be stated in another appropriate place (e.g., in the description of the dataset, in the README file, and/or in the code documentation). In repositories that support multiple publication types, it is recommended to deposit data and code as separate publication types (if possible) to avoid licensing conflicts, linking them through entity relations within the repository (see also [Section Related resources](#)).

CC licenses are recommended for research data. More specialized licenses are suitable for software and databases.

Code can be published with the dataset or separately.

¹⁵ Chue Hong, N., et al. (2022), FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles) (1.0), Research Data Alliance, <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>.

¹⁶ Schlauch, T., et al. (2023), Foundations of Research Software Publication, <https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/hifis/software/education/hifis-workshops/foundations-of-research-software-publication>.

If the curator assumes that the code or software may be of further use, it is recommended to contact the submitter to point out that online services such as GitHub or GitLab would be more suitable publication sites. Since data and code should be licensed differently, it is generally recommended to publish them as separate yet interrelated items with separate licenses. Ideally, code can be published on platforms like GitHub or GitLab and additionally deposited as a scholarly publication in a research repository; to simplify this process, reference should be made to existing publishing pipelines that connect these platforms with specific repositories (e.g., <https://hermes.software-metadata.pub>). The consultation process should address the different preferences regarding the presentation and linking of scripts / code / software with the associated data.

Text modules

Case 1: A non-standardized or non-open license or no license was selected.

You chose to publish your dataset under a non-standardized / non-open license / without a license. For legal certainty, we recommend issuing an open, standardized license such as a Creative Commons license.

Case 2: The dataset contains code (scripts or software) in addition to the actual data.

You have selected the following license for your dataset: [LICENSE NAME]. This license is primarily suitable for publishing simple datasets. Your dataset also contains code. If the code not only works specifically with this data but is also reusable in other ways, we recommend either publishing the code and data separately with mutual references, or publishing the code on a platform like GitLab or GitHub under a suitable software license for everyone to reuse. You can also take advantage of integrations that allow you to push code directly from GitHub to repositories like Zenodo, facilitating proper citation and long-term archiving.

Case 3: The dataset contains predominantly or exclusively code, but was not submitted under a selected software license.

Your dataset appears to primarily contain scripts / code. For regulatory compliance, we recommend granting an open source software license instead of the following license you have chosen: [LICENSE NAME].

3 Sources and further reading

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- KonsortSWD. (2024). *Übersicht Datenzentren*. <https://www.konsortswd.de/angebote/forschende/alle-datenzentren/>
- ORCID. (2023). *ORCID für Forscher*. <https://info.orcid.org/de/researchers/>
- On README files:
 - Dryad (o. D.). *Good data practices*. https://datadryad.org/stash/best_practices#describe-your-dataset-in-a-readme-file
 - Make a README. (o. D.). *Make A README*. <https://www.makeareadme.com/>
- GO FAIR initiative. (2024). *I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data*. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>
- File extension. (o. D.). <https://www.file-extension.info/de>

4 Appendix

4.1 Curation checklist

■ 1. Get an overview of the dataset	
<input type="checkbox"/> Is this research data?	See Text repo vs. data repo
<input type="checkbox"/> Who is the submitting person? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are they eligible to submit? • Are they mentioned among the creators? 	See Creatorship
<input type="checkbox"/> Are recommended details missing? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language • Abstract • README / Documentation • ORCID iD • License • Affiliation • Related resource(s) 	See <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language • Abstract / Summary • README • ORCID iD • Licensing • Affiliation policy of your own institution • Related resources
<input type="checkbox"/> Should access to the dataset be restricted? Should an embargo be established?	See Access restriction and embargo
■ 2. Download the data and take a closer look	
<input type="checkbox"/> Can the files be opened?	See Functional test of the dataset
<input type="checkbox"/> Does the dataset contain personal information?	See Handling of personal information
<input type="checkbox"/> Are the file formats known?	See File formats
<input type="checkbox"/> Are any compressed files or folders included?	See Archive files
<input type="checkbox"/> Are there so many files or such large files that special measures are necessary?	See Size and number
<input type="checkbox"/> Are the data and their origin adequately described? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • if applicable, in the dataset or in the attached document (e.g. README) • Are all abbreviations used expanded? 	See README
<input type="checkbox"/> Is there an obviously more suitable subject-specific repository?	See Recommendation of subject-specific repositories

■ 3. Check metadata	
<input type="checkbox"/> Is the data record submitted to the right location (e.g. in the appropriate collection)?	See Placement within the structure of the repository
<input type="checkbox"/> Is the title meaningful?	See Title
<input type="checkbox"/> Is the title identical to the title of a related resource (e.g. article)?	See Title
<input type="checkbox"/> Are the ORCID iDs specified, and are they correct?	See ORCID iD
<input type="checkbox"/> Are the dates correct?	See Dates
<input type="checkbox"/> Are keywords present? Do they fit?	See Keywords
<input type="checkbox"/> Is the subject assignment correct or missing?	See Subject classification
<input type="checkbox"/> Has a suitable license been granted?	See Licensing
<input type="checkbox"/> Was any access restriction / embargo implemented correctly?	See Access restrictions and embargo
■ 4. After acceptance of the dataset	
<input type="checkbox"/> Register / check DOI	
<input type="checkbox"/> If necessary, set a reminder for later addition of the link to the associated text publication	

4.2 File format recommendations for research data in HeFDI repositories

Researchers are mandated by [Good Research Practice \(GRP\)](#) to retain their research data for at least 10 years and are responsible for considering the usability and readability of the data during this period and, if necessary, beyond. This encompasses a number of issues, such as the ever-increasing volume of data, the development cycles of hardware and software, the ageing of data storage devices, and the question of suitable file formats.

Depending on the collection and method, research data is available in various file formats, each of which has varying suitability for long-term use. When storing data in accordance with the GRP, particular attention should be paid to compatibility with various programs and lossless conversion to alternative formats. Other important criteria include transparency in the form of human and machine readability, as well as the assumed long-term stability of a file format.

This guide recommends file formats for storage in a repository, focusing on the medium-term period of up to 10 years. Long-term archiving, which aims to preserve the usability of data beyond 10 years, requires extensive preparation and active data maintenance. Selecting a suitable file format is good preparation, but it alone is not sufficient to ensure suitability for long-term archiving; likewise, storing data in a research data repository does not cover long-term archiving of the data.

The following table provides a current assessment by the Research Data Management and Data Preservation Unit at ETH Zurich (ETH Library) regarding the suitability of commonly used data formats. This table is based on experience and a detailed evaluation of recommendations and guidelines from international institutions with archiving mandates. The fourth column contains recommendations for converting to more suitable formats. If conversion is possible but results in reduced functionality or a loss of information, we recommend storing the data in both formats. If it is not possible to use a recommended file format, the data will likely no longer be usable 10 years on.

File type	Recommended	Conditionally suitable	Not suitable
text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDF/A (*.pdf, preferred subtypes 2b and 2u) • Unformatted text (*.txt or source code, etc.) encoded as ASCII, UTF-8 or UTF-16 with Byte Order Mark (BOM) • XML (including XSD/XSL/XHTML, etc.; schema & character encoding included) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (*.pdf) with embedded fonts • Unformatted text (.txt, .asc, .c, .h, .cpp, .m, .py, .r, etc.) (ISO 8859-1 encoded) • Rich Text Format (*.rtf) • HTML and XML (without external content) • Word *.docx • PowerPoint *.pptx • LaTeX and TeX (including license-free software packages with special fonts and resulting PDF) • OpenDocument formats (.odm, .odt, .odg, .odc, *.odf) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word *.doc • PowerPoint *.ppt
Spread-sheets and tables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comma- or tab-delimited text files (*.csv) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excel *.xlsx • OpenDocument formats (.odm, .odt, .odg, .odc, *.odf) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excel .xls, .xlsb conversion: to .xlsx
Raw data and workspace		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unformatted text (ASCII encoded) • S-Plus (*.sdd) • Matlab (*.mat) from v7.3 MAT file • Network Common Data Format or NetCDF (.nc, .cdf) • Hierarchical Data Format (HDF5) (.h5, .hdf5, *.he5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matlab files *.mat (binary) Conversion: HDF5 format. • R files *.RData conversion: HDF5 format (with the rhadf package)
Raster graphics (bitmap)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TIFF (*.tif, uncompressed, preferably TIFF 6.0+) • Portable Network Graphics (*.png, uncompressed) • JPEG2000 (*.jp2, lossless compression) • Digital Negative Format (*.dng) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TIFF (*.tif, compressed) • GIF (*.gif) • BMP (*.bmp) • JPEG/JFIF (*.jpg) • JPEG2000 (*.jp2, lossy compression) 	
Vector graphics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SVG without JavaScript binding (*.svg) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphics InDesign (.indd), Illustrator (.ait) • Encapsulated Postscript (*.eps) • Photoshop (*.psd)
Sound, audio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WAV (*.wav) (uncompressed, pulse-code modulated) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Audio Coding (*.mp4) • MP3 (*.mp3) 	
video¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FFV1 codec (from version 3) in Matroska container (*.mkv) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPEG-2 (.mpg, .mpeg) • MP4, also called MPEG-4 Part 14 (*.mp4) • Audio Video Interleave (*.avi) • Motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2, .mjp2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows Media Video (*.wmv) • QuickTime Movie (*.mov)

¹In addition to the file format (or container format), the codec used and the compression type also play an important role.

Source: ETH Zurich, ETH Library [Archivable file formats](#), simplified and commented by [HeFDI](#), [CC-BY 4.0](#)

4.2.1 Further information

For file formats that either do not appear in the recommendations or are described as unsuitable, you should first check whether a format from the recommendation list can be used as an alternative.

To facilitate the handling of data, especially data in non-recommended file formats, and to ensure its usability for as long as possible, we recommend storing a README file with the data. This simple text file describes the context of the data creation, including the software (including version) used to create the data, as well as information on specific measurement instrument settings, coding, and any other information that may help later draw conclusions about how the data can be used.

It increases the chances of long-term usability if embedded objects (such as images, tables, etc.) are also stored as separate files.

During conversion, it is recommended to carefully check the quality of the result visually, for example in the case of texts, especially the formulas, special characters, special fonts.

4.2.2 Further links

[Instructions for converting .docx to .pdf](#)

[Lecture: The PDF/A standard and its different versions](#)

5 Imprint

We would like to thank all colleagues who contributed to the creation of this document in the HeFDI context, in the Open Repo exchange, and beyond.

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If you have any questions or comments regarding this publication, please contact the HeFDI office.

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